

CONTRIBUTIONS OF MUSIC TO INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT - EMPIRICAL AND LOGICAL

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme related to the contributions of music to intellectual development – empirically and logically. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it brings to the broad discussion a potential instrument for expanding creative capacity, and for that purpose systematic investigative studies of a comparative empirical nature should be applied until it approaches facts that prove or disprove the results. Its social relevance lies in the fact that music is a public element, widely accessible and, by allowing children to have contact with it from an early age, guided by capable teachers, this provides a deeper knowledge about the object-object of work and delight . This is a theoretical investigation, discussed from a critical-analytical point of view, based on competent authors in the subject. The aim of this study is to discuss the importance of music in Early Childhood Education and its contributions to the overall development of the child. Thus, this study was an attempt to answer the following research questions: What is the importance of using music with children in the context of Early Childhood Education? How can music contribute to the integral development of the child? Music education in childhood should not only be carried out with the aim of developing an interest and taste for music, or even for the acquisition of musical knowledge and learning an instrument, but rather to provide a conscious musical experience. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a learning project and adequate teaching planning in Art classes, so that students can have broad experiences with music and musical instruments.

Keywords: Music. music education. Intellectual development. Musicalization in the school educational space.

INTRODUCTION

Music is part of human existence and this is a proven fact, since, even before man existed, it already existed and had a purpose in the animal kingdom. With the advent of language development, it is incorporated into its framework and does not cease to enchant as much as it intrigues, given its dimension of fixation in memory and thought.

With the advancement of research in the field of education and its search for expanding ways to enhance learning, through various pedagogical and didactic strategies, music was adopted as one more of these elements that can help and contribute to the broader process acquisition of learning the contents that are applied, in a systematic way, in the classes.

The challenge is how music can contribute to expanding the potential of cognitive, empirical and logical learning. For each of these situations, different areas of the brain are activated and, in the case in question, it can serve as a *leitmotiv* to revive the data in memory and, thus, contribute to their processing, with greater ease and objectivity.

In the specific case of the development of pedagogical work, the use of music in education is not intended to train professional musicians or to teach how to compose songs or anything like that; the idea is to share the benefits arising from this practice, making it part of the pedagogical framework of formal education. However, one cannot lose sight of the fact that this requires studies, research and investment in training professionals, acquiring instruments, access to shows in various formats, from classical music to rock, with the intention of discovering which one best suits the work applied in the classroom by the teacher and that is described in the school educational curriculum and in the teaching plans (individual and collective). Inserting music in the school curriculum is something that has been done since ancient times, noting that it was already part of the *Trivium* and *Quadrivium*; however, care must be taken not to apply something about Pedagogy *to forceps*, without direction, without a transparent and defined objective and without empirical knowledge of what can be obtained as a result of such action.

This work is a theoretical outline on the contribution of music to cognitive learning processes, empirical and theoretical, and cannot be understood as a definitive answer to the need for broad comparative studies to be carried out in partnership with the various fields of scientific and academic knowledge.

ABOUT THE MUSIC

Music has always been associated with the traditions and cultures of each era. Currently, the technological development applied to communications has been modifying, in a considerable way, the musical references of the societies by the possibility of a simultaneous listening of all world production, through disks, tapes, radio, television, computer, electronic games, cinema, publicity, *etc.*

The process of creating a musical composition is driven by the intention of the composer from a project that intends to generate a song. Among the sounds of the voice, the environment, known instruments, other sound materials or electronically obtained, the composer can choose one of them, consider its basic parameters (duration, pitch, timbre and intensity), combine it with other sounds and silences building elements of several other orders and organizing everything in a way to constitute a syntax. He can also compose music by combining it with other languages, as in songs, soundtracks for movies or electronic games, *jingles* for advertising, music for dance and music for rituals or celebrations. In this type of production, the composer considers the limits established by each language, in particular.

Peixoto (2007) is categorical in stating that,

Since music is expressed through sounds, a work that has not yet been interpreted only exists as music in the mind of the composer who conceived it. The moment of interpretation is when the project or score becomes living music. Interpretations are important in learning, as both direct contact with them and their use as a model are ways for students to build knowledge in music. In addition, interpretations establish the contexts where elements of musical language gain meaning. Improvisations are situated between compositions and interpretations. These are moments of composition coinciding with moments of interpretation. In learning, improvisation activities must take place in well-structured proposals so that creative freedom can be achieved through awareness of limits. A look at the entire production of music in the world reveals the existence of numerous processes and systems of composition or improvisation and all of them have their importance in terms of activities in the classroom (PEIXOTO, 2007, p. 101).

From the point of view of organizing the heights of sounds, the modal/tonal system, which was at the base of the music of practically all cultures until the 19th century, remains today as the great reference, even for composers who created their own systems. Its inclusion as content in this document is intended to ensure the presence in fundamental education of the most elaborate syntax that man has ever conceived to make music, giving students greater opportunities to develop knowledge about the activity and thus be able to express their potential creativity musical.

Studying the modal/tonal system in Brazil, through local, regional, national and international cultures, helps to know the mother tongue and its variants. Figuring among the most important musical traditions, songs are compositions produced in this system, being responsible for a significant portion of the country's musical production, including those broadcast on the market.

Brazilian songs constitute a very vast field of possibilities for teaching music and can be part of musical productions in the classroom, allowing the student to elaborate hypotheses regarding the degree of precision needed for tuning, rhythm, perception of elements language, simultaneities , *etc.*

In classroom music productions, it is important to understand very clearly the difference between composition and performance. In a song, for example, elements such as melody or lyrics are part of the composition; however, the song is only present through interpretation in the company of all the other elements: instruments, arrangements in their formal conception, basic arrangements with their rhythmic patterns, interpretative characteristics, improvisations , *etc.*

The experienced performer knows how to allow the most subtle nuances of the song being interpreted to be inscribed in his voice, which then becomes the bearer of a large number of elements of the musical language. In order to be able to do the same, the student needs the interpretations as a reference and time to develop his musical and rhythmic thinking, from them, until he acquires conditions to incorporate the song with all its elements. In this process, he follows the same principle of assimilation and accommodation of previous knowledge, fixing it in his long-term memory, a process that can be classified as *musical literacy*. The song also offers the possibility of contact with all the richness and profusion of individual, local, national and international rhythms, which are categorically manifested in it through one of its most important elements: the basic arrangement. In activities with this element, it is important to remember that music is considered both a samba drumming and a song that uses it as a basic arrangement. This is an overly broad vision of the music process and, not necessarily, of music itself. Nonetheless,

So that music learning can be fundamental in the formation of citizens, it is necessary that everyone has the opportunity to participate [...], involving people from outside in the enrichment of teaching and promoting interaction with musical and artistic groups from the localities, the school can help students become sensitive listeners, talented amateurs, or professional musicians. Encouraging participation in concerts, festivals, concerts, popular culture events and other musical manifestations, it can provide conditions for a rich and broad appreciation where the student learns to value the important

moments in which music is inscribed in time and history (BARBOSA and SALES, 2005, p. 93).

What the authors claim is that music is and should be considered as an instrument that enables the formation of social thought through its promotion to the greatest possible number of individuals and learning and teaching situations, interaction and symbolic exchanges. They confuse music learning, as a technique, with learning to appreciate good music, in which, for that, it is necessary to participate in events of any musical nature.

ABOUT MUSICALIZATION IN THE SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL SPACE

Studies such as those by Bréscia (2003), Nogueira (2004) and Weigel (1998), show that the child still in the maternal womb can feel and perceive external vibrations, which induces many mothers to listen to music, believing that this can help in the development of your babies. In fact, this action can greatly contribute to a healthy pregnancy and a balanced and serene fetal development process. It must be clarified that it is not music, in itself, that promotes a healthy development of the fetus, as if it could perform miracles and other wonders impossible to be explained by logic; is its effect on the emotional state of the pregnant woman, acting in a way to reassure her and, with this, helping her to produce endorphin, which makes the babies, still in the womb, remain calm. Bréscia (2003, p. 41), in turn, states that “the scientific investigation of the psychological aspects and processes linked to music is as old as the origins of psychology.”

Since antiquity, the first thinkers already understood the power that music had on human behavior and sought, from such knowledge, to elaborate ways to extract benefits from it. Greek mythology, in particular, is full of episodes in which music served to calm the fiercest tempers of men, gods and beasts. The myth of Opheu descending into the subterranean realms is the most profound of them all and it demonstrates the real power of music.

Bréscia (2003) states that singing is an excellent learning companion in general and that it contributes a lot to socialization, learning concepts and discovering the world. For Weigel (1998), activities with music can contribute a lot as reinforcement in the child's psychomotor and affective development. Research by Nogueira (2004), on the other hand, dating from the end of the 20th century, confirms that the greater the musical stimulus that the child receives, the greater will be their potential for intellectual development, because when working with sounds and their auditory development, they your motor coordination and attention will also be developed.

Thinking about the issue of child development along with music, Brito (2003, p. 43) argues that, “the child gradually develops his language as he comes into contact with the spelling and reading of words and also with the music itself.” According to him,

The language acquisition process also facilitates the comparison with musical expression: from the vocal exploration phase to the reproduction phase, creation and recognition of the first letters, from there to the spelling of words, then to phrases and, finally, to reading and writing. , there is a path that involves the permanent reorganization of perceptions, explorations, discoveries, construction of hypotheses, reflections and meanings that make all transformations and achievements of knowledge meaningful: consciousness in continuous movement. This also occurs with music (Idem, 2003, p. 43).

What the author points out is that learning music requires taking a long path, in which well-defined steps must be followed until the condition of elaborating logical thinking about music and the elements that integrate it is reached and that , once put together result in enchanting compositions. What cannot be lost sight of is that all this needs action, direct contact with the instruments, rehearsals, dedication, training, discipline.

Gainza (1998) and Brito (2003), state that the manipulation of musical instruments and the type of contact with music contributes to the development of the child's musical creativity and also to their motor development, in addition to working with their imagination. , encouraging her. In this regard,

Building musical instruments and/or sound objects is an activity that arouses children's curiosity and interest. In addition to contributing to the understanding of elementary issues related to the production of sound and its qualities, acoustics, the mechanism and functioning of musical instruments, the construction of instruments stimulates research, imagination, planning, organization, creativity , being, therefore, a great way to develop the capacity to elaborate and execute projects. It is important to suggest ideas, present ready-made models and also encourage the creation of new musical instruments (BRITO, 2003, p. 69).

In any case, the construction of instruments, in addition to providing performance in terms of motor development, increasing the ability to execute and design projects, creativity can also be used to establish a healthy and important relationship with other cultures, based on the idea of mix sounds from different instruments, originating from different peoples.

Brito (2003) corroborates this thought when he states that the activity of building instruments will be richer and more meaningful if relationships are established with the history of musical instruments and their role over time, in different cultures. Therefore, it is important

to show books on the subject, ethnic and regional instruments, listen to different recordings and also get in touch with instruments, considering that,

By building musical instruments, children retrace, in their own way, the path traced by us, human beings, in the search for means to exercise musical expression, at the same time that they transcend this path through the invention of new possibilities (BRITO, 2003, p. 70).

Thinking about the importance that this experience can provide for the child, Brito (2003) recommends working back to the past of different cultures through musical instruments, even as a way of not just a loose and aimless construction of musical instruments. The author thus understands that the presence of music in Early Childhood Education can contribute directly and positively not only to the musical formation of the child, but mainly to human development, since music works with various aspects such as cognition, creativity and expression. Despite this contribution, the presence of music in Education provides the respect, friendship, cooperation and reflection that are so important and necessary for human development, not to mention that it can make the teaching and learning environment more joyful and interesting, seeking to capture the attention of the child, facilitating the understanding of the information by the student.

Brito (2003, p. 45) states directly to the educator the importance of his work:

Obviously, respecting the development process of children's musical expression should not be confused with the absence of educational interventions. In this sense, the teacher must act – always – as an animator, stimulator, provider of information and experiences that will enrich and expand the experience and knowledge of children, not only from a musical point of view, but integrally, which should be the objective. priority of every pedagogical proposal, especially in the early childhood education stage.

There is no doubt that music plays a very important role in the integral development of the child. However, one cannot forget the figure of the educator in this process. He often does not have the preparation to work with music in the classroom, nor does he find resources such as a variety of instruments to develop music classes. With regard to the issue of the availability of didactic resources for use by teachers, Brito (2003) proposes the construction of musical instruments with the children themselves in the classroom.

Brescia (2003) will state that,

To build instruments, it is necessary, first of all, to select and organize the material that will be used: scrap and recyclable materials, cans, cardboard boxes, plastic pots, packaging, cardboard, PVC and conduit tubes, etc. It is also important to have grains, seeds, gourds, shells, pebbles, corks, rubber

bands, nylon threads, bladders, masking tape, scissors, glue, pins, nails, screws, saws, hammers, pliers, screwdrivers, as well as paints, strings, colored tape and other materials, used to finish and decorate the created objects (BRÉSCIA, 2003, p. 70).

In this way, it can be observed that there is a vast arsenal of materials that can be used for the manufacture of musical instruments. In the view of Brito (2003), the important thing is the planning of what will be done and the obtaining of the materials that can be done through the help of the children themselves who can bring simple materials from home through the request of the teacher together with those responsible for the student. In any case, the school must ensure equal opportunities for all children, in the sense that they can have access to music and be educated musically, whatever the socio-cultural environment they come from, as Mársico puts it well (1982).

Considering the premise of an equitable and quality music education in schools, Brito (2003) draws attention to the question of the learning time and musical development of each child, since there are students who present great ease in musical development and those who present some difficulties which is normal when it comes to learning.

Within this issue, argues Souza and Joly (2010, p. 100), that it is necessary to rethink the expectations that one has of the objective of music classes in Basic Education, because in school, “musical teaching has no intention of forming musicians. professional”; its intention is to provide an additional condition of sensory experience for students and teachers, and may even lead to a discovery of talents, a vocation for music.

In the same line of thought, for Mársico (1982), educators must be careful not to explore only the musical side of the child, which can cause frustration and lack of interest in the arts, if the child does not have a greater ability for music. “Musical activities at school are not aimed at training musicians, but rather, through experience and understanding, provide the opening of sensory channels, facilitating the expression of emotions, expanding general culture and contributing to the integral formation of the being” (MÁRSICO, 1982, p. 148).

Music can be associated with well-being, reflection, a condition of harmonizing the environment (and not people or what they feel) and this leads to one feeling more calm and balanced, emotionally, within the living space. with others. When one thinks about this technique and what it produces and more, what students can create, from its mastery, a whole scope of pedagogical resourcefulness is transformed into learning possibilities that, in turn, are transmuted into different experiential situations than one might expect for a conventional class; this is because a differentiated element was inserted in the pedagogical action, highlighting music and its variations, didactic possibilities and potential.

The educator must work with music teaching in order to improve the child's learning and development, because with music it is possible to improve the motor, concentration, disciplinary, emotional and adaptation aspects of the child, which according to Brito (2003, p. 46), when the teacher chooses to work with music, he certainly has the conviction that “what matters primarily is the child, the subject of the experience, and not the music, as many musical teaching situations insist on consider. Music education should not aim at training possible musicians of tomorrow, but at the comprehensive training of today's children.”

What is expected, with music, played in the educational environment as a curricular subject, is that it promotes the maximum empirical interaction of students with music and its variants, including musical production and composition instruments. A well-elaborated and well-conducted work plan means that learning music and its processes are treated as transdisciplinary aspects linked to all fields of knowledge, ranging from when music is studied from the knowledge of the Pythagorean philosophers, through Orpheus and his lyre to the rhapsodes, who went from town to town in Greece, singing and reciting the deeds of great heroes.

However, the school must be very careful not to transform the music discipline into a theoretical repertoire without the capacity to take someone anywhere, which, as a rule, happens with an enchanting frequency, due to the simple fact that one is hired to teach professional classes who are not trained in music, taking care to try to meet a curricular requirement, without the slightest concern with learning the organized systematic content and its pragmatic functions.

Learning in all senses presupposes a mechanical effort on the target object that one intends to master and, together, a work of knowledge of the techniques used to reach the pace concerning what is intended. In the specific case of music, it is divided into paradigms, in which, on the one hand, there is mastery of a technique that ranges from learning how to play music, composing, making arrangements and, simply, its application together to the didactic methods, becoming a teaching strategy. In both cases, a very well-organized plan must be elaborated, understanding that when proposing the insertion of music in the classes, what it has is its transformation into an auxiliary instrument and/or enhancer of learning, being responsible for evaluations from then on. empirical, in order to know the real dimension of what it was possible to achieve with its use for this specific purpose.

Gainza (1998) defending that music can go far beyond the contribution to learning and cognitive development of the child, expresses his opinion, arguing that,

Music moves, mobilizes, and therefore contributes to transformation and development. Each of the aspects or elements of the music corresponds to a specific human aspect which it mobilizes with bodily exclusivity, melody stimulates affectivity; the musical order or structure (in harmony or musical form) actively contributes to the affirmation or restoration of mental order in man (GAINZA, 1998, p. 36).

As can be seen, music is considered not only as a didactic resource, but also as a form of therapy, since it contributes to an improvement in the living conditions of individuals with mental difficulties. This is due, according to Guilherme (2006, p. 158), to the fact that “music is one of the most powerful stimuli to activate the circuits of the brain”, reinforcing the memory and the parameters linked to it, directly and indirectly. Rhythms, sounds, cadences, everything mixes and connects to the empirical and logical mechanisms of mnemonic action in such a way that various brain fields are motivated, producing synapses and thought chains. In this sense, the teacher must rethink the teaching of Art so that there is a re-elaboration of contents and methodological strategies, in which singing and listening to music can be meant as a way of promoting the integral development of the individual, from the earliest age.

In the same way that telling children bedtime stories, singing to them, any song whatsoever, especially those that provoke a relaxation of the anxiety and fear of everyday life, something more common among children, serves to help them fall asleep safely and have a peaceful sleep. Hence to say that it was music itself that performed a miracle is folly; it is important to emphasize the increase in learning potential, if the individual does not feel concerned about his own personal safety, being able to allocate a much larger portion of energy to empirical tasks, such as the observation of phenomena and their occurrences, being able to transform these scientific activities into logical things.

Vieira da Cunha (1999, p. 123) when considering the specificity of music, with all its active processes (hearing, singing, dancing, body and instrumental percussion, melodic creation), stresses that: “[...] music naturally globalizes the various aspects to be activated in the child's development: cognitive/linguistic, psychomotor, affective/social”.

This is a somewhat exaggerated statement that lacks empirical evidence, and it is possible to state that music provides aesthetics to dance, to the development of bodily cadences in which a series of mechanical and logical actions happens rhythmically, obeying the training and rules of balance and harmony. However, taking this as a way of saying that it causes miracles is, once again, to fall in contrast with scientific investigation, in which experience is taken as a starting point to arrive at the formulation of theories.

Several empirical studies and investigations need to be conducted, with music as a *leitmotif* and the results compared with situations in which it was absent. The school offers a formal educational service, so your response should be within the scope of providing blunt and accurate details about the services it offers and not just an empty hope for nothing. Heated statements, based simply on individual belief cannot mean elements that guide the educational work provided under the direct tutelage of the State.

Each element that is being incorporated into the educational scope needs to be duly tested and approved, with factual results capable of being reproduced on a large scale. It is a known fact that music has the power to mobilize feelings and mnemonic affections; but providing learning or facilitating it is a reason for deeper empirical investigations and this, not because the hypotheses suggested so far are not credible; but, because it is about investments in techniques, strategies, methodologies, training, direct and indirect costs, in which one is crossed by the expectation of a feasible return.

In the midst of all this didactic undertaking, it is necessary to know what to apply, at what age to apply it and how to apply it, considering that the inclusion of music in formal basic education does not have the direct intention of training professional musicians, rather, to add a tool that can assist in the development of students' cognitive skills. To say that they will become more creative, which, in Dau's (2023) conception is the expression of intelligence, is to fall into a serious risk of not having understood how human thought works.

To stimulate creativity and learning, Souza and Joly (2010) suggest the development of exploring games, such as playing with sound objects that are within reach, experimenting with the possibilities of your voice and imitating what you hear is something very positive for the child. The contact with these games will allow the student to be able to “[...] categorize and give meaning to sounds that were previously isolated, grouping them in a way that they begin to make sense to her” (SOUZA; JOLY, 2010, p. 98).

Still according to the authors mentioned, through this contact all areas of child development can be reinforced. However, music represents an invaluable benefit for the formation and balance of the child's and adolescent's personality . In fact, once it is inserted into the individual universe of each human being, it never leaves it. Freud, for example, could not study listening to music; however, nowadays this has become the most natural condition, in which a huge range of students can be observed who do it, without any damage to mechanical concentration.

Speaking of cognitive development, it is important to remember that the child is a dynamic being, who interacts with the environment, an interaction that causes mental structures

to be built and ways to be acquired for it to function, as presented by Piaget (1481-1565 dH) that, through play, for example, the child discovers the world through his interaction with objects and people , and begins to understand the world that surrounds him, understanding its events and systematizing his ideas into a whole with its own meanings (FUSARI ; FERRAZ, 1992).

Therefore, accompanying the teacher's or classmates' gestures, conducting music, participating in the rhythmic band, imitating birdsong, animal voices or other sounds existing in nature, are essential musical experiences for the child's intellectual development, since your thinking is being organized . “And the more they have the opportunity to compare the actions performed and the sensations obtained through music, the more their intelligence, their knowledge [*empirical, in this field*] develops” (FERREIRA, 2002, p. 15).

One cannot take the elevation of logic, in a globalized way, from a simple action or insertion of a single element, as if it were capable of performing wonders, by itself. The process involves building a learning project in which music becomes a strategic object in this pedagogical scope. The process of intelligence development, in general terms, as Pinto (2009) explains, begins with hearing, as it uses sound codes that represent spaces activated in the brain to retain that information. The cited author complements this information by adding that:

The neurons, which receive coded information, after being activated by the musical codes, would be “open” to receive knowledge from other sense organs. And that the activation of neurons would be increased as new knowledge is added through the five sense organs. The greater the sound knowledge of the person the more different sounds he hears, as he is using a larger brain area to retain that information (PINTO, 2009, p. 15).

Thus, musical teaching would be one more possibility for the individual's intellectual development, thus having a significant weight for the success of the learning process. Hence the importance of children's contact with the world of music from an early age, for a greater chance of assimilating new sound codes that music can offer (PINTO, 2009). The diversity of different sounds that the child can hear in everyday life (and its amplification), can equally contribute to the practice of a musical instrument. This whole musical learning process represents, in short, a way of generating opportunities for cognitive development.

Following this reasoning, Pinto (2009) emphasizes the need to encourage music learning; because, in that case, it would serve as a way for the person to express their feelings, their emotions, convey their messages, develop their sensitivity, creativity and imagination. Knowing this, it is easy to understand the importance of working on learning music in Basic Education, specifically in Early Childhood Education.

Coletto (2010, p. 29) corroborates, in this sense, when he writes that “it is important to work on Art in Early Childhood Education, because through them the child can express himself from a young age either with a drawing or a song, he can express his feelings, emotions, thoughts, thus allowing us to know each one more”.

Unique opportunities to get to know each other, a little more about individual expression and conflict situations to which children are subjected in their daily lives and homes. Dealing specifically with psychomotor development, Bueno (1998) is referred to, when he places the need to know the degree of development of the muscles, bones and nervous system of students as an indispensable basic element for working with physical activities at school.

For the child to develop specific activities in a natural way, he needs to reach a certain stage of motor development. The motor maturation process of the human being must occur as he grows, that is, gradually. However, the child's motor skills can be improved thanks to performing musical activities at school and in their everyday life. Notably, those children who have the opportunity to interact with the musical universe control their body better, improve gross motor coordination (big movements) and fine (small movements), move with ease (FERREIRA, 2002).

As Pinto reinforces (2009, p. 13):

The activities carried out in musicalization classes collaborate and help the development of body movements, stimulating gestures and movements requested in the activities. The innumerable possibilities offered by musical games even allow working the musculature of the arms, legs, feet, hands and fingers and this learning is necessary from the first year of life.

Thinking about this dynamic of evolution of psychomotor development, Fonterrada (2008) and Ilari (2002) suggest the practice of playing songs, including those from folklore, rhymes, specifically those that present suggestions of body movements that provide benefits in motor coordination and other skills. as auditory and visual.

These are interesting situations in which learning situations from other disciplines can be inserted, carrying out an interdisciplinary work of a high pedagogical and didactic nature. What is intended is to introduce science into the world of children, without it seeming like an aggression or an obligation, at a time when they are not mature enough, from a cognitive point of view, to do so. In this way, she can sing, play, create verses from her own autonomous linguistic domain and, according to Pinto (2009, p. 12):

When the child sings, or is involved with sound interpretation roles in the community, he feels integrated into the group and becomes aware that his knowledge is equally important. She understands the need for cooperation

with colleagues, to reach the common goal. When the child studies music together, it becomes more communicative and coexists all the time with rules of socialization. The child learns to respect the time and will of others; to criticize constructively; to have discipline; The listen and interact with the group.

Due to its social and affective power, according to Abramovich (1985), musicalization as a pedagogical strategy has become one of the most important areas of knowledge to be worked on in Basic Education, ranging from Kindergarten to High School. Undoubtedly, music has very significant effects on the child's socio-affective development.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The aim of this study was to discuss the importance of music in Early Childhood Education and its contributions to the overall development of the child. Thus, this study was an attempt to answer the following research questions: What is the importance of using music with children in the context of Early Childhood Education? How can music contribute to the integral development of the child ?

Once these guiding questions have been presented, from here on some considerations related to the objective of this study and its possible contributions are presented. It was found that music is present in the lives of human beings since the beginning of the prehistoric period. Countless factors have determined its evolution over time, in various cultures, that is, according to place and time, music has been disseminated and developed, until it reaches the way it is represented today.

It was also found that music (the art of the muses) basically consists of a succession of sounds and silence organized over time. Here, making children musical can be about awakening and developing spontaneous expression , sensitivity and taste for music, stimulating and contributing to their global formation. To this end, the educator can develop musical-pedagogical activities to create a bond and a taste between music and the child. In Early Childhood Education, these activities should allow children to participate in games that involve singing, listening and dancing to children's songs and nursery rhymes, for example.

Education in childhood should not only be carried out with the aim of developing an interest and taste for music, or even for the acquisition of musical knowledge and learning an instrument, but rather to provide a conscious musical experience . Therefore, it is necessary to develop a learning project and adequate teaching planning in Art classes, so that students can have broad experiences with music and musical instruments.

The most relevant finding is that the inclusion of music in Early Childhood Education makes it possible to carry out a comprehensive education. Working with music tends to innovate the learning process, or even renew pedagogical practices, when music is used with children.

From the knowledge learned and outlined here, it can be conceived that the teaching and learning of music in schools has been recognized by renowned authors of literature as a great ally in the cognitive, emotional and social development of learners. Enabling the constant interest of students and the rescue of musical joy, providing an integral and pleasurable learning experience.

Based on this study, the use of music in the education of students in the early childhood stage of education is reiterated, given that when applied to this population, reasoning, creativity, sensitivity and perception are developed, in addition to promoting self-discipline, thus favoring the interpretation and understanding of the world, and helps them build their autonomy in the midst of their learning process.

Thus, it is necessary to be concerned with the role of the Early Childhood Education professional, since children in this educational modality are in constant development and learning, so this teacher can, through music, shorten the path and facilitate the development of children. It is believed that he should know how to correctly and positively stimulate his learning. For this, he must research, plan, diagnose and help the student to build his knowledge by experiencing the different ways of *making music*. If it is used correctly, the Early Childhood Education professional can have an easier development, in addition to more sociable and calmer children.

As a technical resource, the need for musical and pedagogical-musical training in Pedagogy courses is pointed out, given that the teacher's educational practice has an intense impact on the education of children.

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